

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Osmium in Micro-quantities with Benzyldimethylphenylammonium Chloride

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Benzyldimethylphenylammonium (BDPA) chloride, a quaternary ammonium salt, possesses considerable potentiality to find application as a reagent for the determination of a number of metal ions present in micro-quantities in solution. Preparation of the compound is very simple¹, and its purity can be checked up without much difficulty. Yoshimura and Ueno² used BDPA chloride for the spectrophotometric determination of a number of metal ions. In the present investigation, it is found that in presence of dilute hydrochloric acid, the ion-association complex formed between a hexachloro-osmium(IV) and a BDPA cation is extracted into 1,2-dichloroethane in presence of a little amount of dimethylformamide and its absorbance at 343 and 376 nm are utilised for the spectrophotometric determination of osmium. Beer's law is obeyed for 32–280 µg Os/10 ml extract in the final solution. The molar absorptivities are 3.676×10^4 and 2.74×10^4 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 343 and 376 nm respectively.

Osmium(IV) forms a yellow coloured ion-association complex of the type [BDPA]₂[OsCl₆] in dilute hydrochloric acid. The colour intensity remains same when the acidity of the aqueous phase is in the range 0.001–0.09 M with respect to hydrochloric acid. Unless the BDPA chloride is added, the complex is not extractable in 1,2-dichloroethane. The concentration of BDPA chloride in the aqueous layer should be in the range 0.06–0.12 M without which the absorbance value shows a diminishing tendency. Dimethyl-

formamide is added to dissolve the light yellow precipitate formed after addition of BDPA chloride. Addition of dimethylformamide makes the extraction easier and increases the stability and colour intensity of the extracted species. The absorbance remains constant over a period of at least 12 h. If the amount of dimethylformamide added is less than 1 ml and higher than 3 ml, the absorbance is lower.

The tolerance limit for interferences was set at the amount required to cause an error not exceeding about 1% in the determination of osmium, but the upper concentration limit investigated was restricted to 50-fold (w/w) ratio to osmium. The following foreign ions (I) caused no interference at I : Os weight ratio : acetate ≤ 50; Cd^{II}, Mn^{II} ≤ 42; fluoride, oxalate, EDTA, Zn^{II} ≤ 37; thiocyanate, sulphite ≤ 30; As^{III}, As^V, thiosulphate ≤ 15; Co^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Pb^{II} ≤ 7.5; Ni^{II}, Pd^{II}, Cu^{II}, Au^{III}, Sn^{II}, V^V, Ir^{III}, Cr^{III}, bromide, iodide, citrate, tartrate, thiourea, cyanide ≤ 4.5; W^{VI}, Ag^I, Bi^{III}, Rh^{III} ≤ 2.5; Sb^{III}, Mo^{VI}, Mn^{VII} ≤ 1.0. The tolerance limit for some of the interfering species could be improved by use of masking agents, e.g. Cr^{VI} with sulphite and Hg^{II} with EDTA. Pt^{IV} if present, requires prior removal. Gold interferes if absorbance is measured at 343 nm but shows no interference at 376 nm.

The method was successfully applied for determination of osmium in different synthetic mixtures containing diverse ions.

A standard solution containing $18.9 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of osmium was estimated (10 times) by the recommended procedure. The average absorbance was 0.3653 at 343 nm and 0.2731 at 376 nm with standard deviations of 0.002 and 0.003 absorbance unit respectively. Sandell's sensitivities are 0.0517 and $0.0692 \mu\text{g Os/cm}^2$ at 343 and 376 nm respectively. The molar absorptivities are 3.676×10^4 at 343 and $2.74 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 376 nm. The operation time in each run is 5–10 min. Good recovery of osmium was achieved in presence of most of the common ions and the results were accurate and precise to a high degree.

Experimental

A U-3210 Hitachi spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

The stock solution of osmium was prepared from osmium tetrachloride (CPC, A division of Centrechem Inc. Philadelphia) and was standardised³. Solutions of lower concentrations were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. The reagent BDPA chloride was prepared by mixing equimolar amounts of benzyl chloride and dimethylaniline and allowing the mixture to stand until crystallisation was effected. The solid after washing with acetone was recrystallised from

alcohol. A 0.1 M solution of BDPA chloride was used for the determination of osmium. All chemicals used were of analytical grade.

An aliquot of sample solution containing 32–280 μg of Os^{IV} was diluted with HCl so that after addition of 0.1 M BDPA chloride solution (1 ml) in water, the acidity of the aqueous phase remained in the range 0.001–0.09 M with respect to HCl. Then dimethylformamide (2 ml), followed by 1,2-dichloroethane (10 ml) were added. The mixture was then shaken for 30 s and the organic layer separated. The absorbance of the extract was measured at 343 and 376 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of osmium in unknown solution was computed using a standard calibration curve.

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